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Linguistic distance as a variable of the gravity model for international trade: example of China

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This article investigates the role of linguistic distance on bilateral trade by using a set of indicators aimed to depict linguistic distance or proximity of China and its major trade partners. For this purpose, the gravity model that uses the linguistic distance as one of the elements of analysis and forecasting of bilateral trade is utilized. To achieve this goal, existing theories of the gravitational model are considered, the concept of linguistic distance is defined and its expediency to be included in the gravitational model justified. As a result, the impact of linguistic distance on bilateral trade is measured.

Keywords: *international trade, linguistic distance, gravity model of trade, communication costs, economy of language.*

Introduction

Linguistic distance, meaning the incompatibility between two spoken languages or/and writing systems, is an important factor affecting international economic interactions such as trade or migration by creating additional non-economic obstacles and increasing transaction costs. These additional expenses caused by the language factor can be observed at the macroeconomic level; the relatively higher, profitable or more intense trade between countries with similar languages is an indisputable fact of the modern international economy. It is plottable and predictable that the trade between countries with a common language is normally easier than between countries with different languages and thus the transaction expenses are lower.

Giving the nature of the contemporary global economic environment, the ascension of Asian economic powers such as China, Korea, and Viet Nam, IT-innovations and informatization of all sectors of the economy it is becoming increasingly important to evaluate the impact of language factor on international trade.

Theoretical framework

The concept of linguistic distance and its measurement are actively discussed among linguists and economists. In

their research, P. Chiswick & B. Miller (1994, 2005) proved that linguistic diversity and linguistic distance are significantly affecting communication and thus are important indicators of the performance of economic cooperation. Specifically, as a determinant of bilateral trade linguistic distance was examined by W. K. Hutchinson (2005); the question on whether a trade is affected by language was also studied by Kwan Choi (2002) and J. Lohmann (2011). The role of linguistic distance in the applied economy was further outlined by Ispording & Otten (2013). However despite obvious interest expressed by many scholars and researchers linguistic distance (or proximity) remains a new subject in economic theory and requires additional research and analysis especially when it concerns countries that use languages and writing systems different from the Indo-European language family.

Because of its role in the contemporary global economy, language of not widespread Sino-Tibetan family and unique writing system China is of interest to such research. According to Kwan Choi (2002) commodities of Chinese origins are additionally hindered by language factor when facing promotion on the global market because it is unlikely for Mandarin to become a universal language of the trade while the cost of translation from Chinese is considerably higher than in case of more closely related languages. The latter is particularly important for international trade, as literacy affects not only negotiation and commercial

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contracting but also the price of goods, since language localization of products requires additional costs, especially for countries with significantly different writing systems, which is especially true in case of Chinese goods, with which promotion on the world market is severely impeded by the language factor.

The purpose of the study

The purpose of the following article is to assess the influence of linguistic distance on bilateral trade relations on the example of China, to build a gravity model that will use the linguistic distance as one of the elements of analysis and forecasting of bilateral trade. To achieve this goal, existing theories of the gravitational model of international trade were considered, the concept of linguistic distance was defined and it's expediency to be included in the gravitational model justified.

The idea that the language may influence trade is closely related to the theory and usage of the gravity model in

economics which is a widespread method of analyzing and predicting bilateral trade. The theoretical foundation for the gravity model of trade was introduced in the works of Walter Isard (1954), modified by Tinbergen (1962) and since then became a constant topic of theoretical studies and macroeconomic modeling. The idea of including the linguistic factor in the gravity model of trade was recently discussed in the studies of Ribeiro & Ferro (2016), and Farhat Fasih (2018).

Theoretical framework

The gravity model of trade is based on Newton's law of universal gravitation. In its traditional form, the gravity model states that the bilateral trade between the two countries is proportional to the sizes of their economies (usually measured by GDP) and inversely proportional to the distance between them. Originally the gravity equation of international trade was introduced by Isard (1954) in the following formula:

$$T_{ij} = G \times \frac{Y_i \times Y_j}{D_{ij}} \varepsilon_{ij} \quad (1)$$

Where T_{ij} stands for the total trade between countries i and j ; Y_i, Y_j stands for the GDP of the respected countries; D_{ij} for the distance between them in kilometers; G for the gravity constant (the theorized influence of the gravity force

similar to the Newtonian gravity); ε_{ij} for an error term with expectation equal to 1.

In more recent studies it is common practice to use a log-log model suitable for consequent Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression:

$$\ln T_{ij} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \ln(Y_i) + \alpha_2 \ln(Y_j) + \alpha_3 \ln(D_{ij}) + \alpha_4 DV1 + \alpha_5 DV2 + \alpha_6 DV3 + \dots + \varepsilon_{ij} \quad (2)$$

Where constant G becomes part of α_0 and DV 1, 2, 3... stands for different dummy variables aimed to describe quality factors, i.e. such determinants of bilateral trade as the common language, cultural similarity, shared colonial past, membership in trade blocs and alliances, etc. All of these dummy variables are aimed to describe the easiness or complexity of dealing in trade with a particular partner, each additional dummy theoretically makes the model more reliable but on the other hand, makes it harder to interpret since with each additional variable the results become complex. It is obvious that dummy variables need to be meaningful and do not duplicate one another as can often be observed with linguistic, language and cultural variables.

In his extensive work on gravity model and linguistic proximity Farhat Fasih (2018) proposes to replace the traditional language dummy variable with the Linguistic Proximity Index defined as explained by Adserà & Pytliková (2015). This index is constructed as the sum of four weights (levels of linguistic family tree) and may take values such as 0, 0.1, 0.2... 1 depending on their combination. This method may seem more substantiated since it is considering more variations than just the similarity or difference of language however the usage of a complex indicator next to linear log in the same regression as well as the mix of quantity and quality indicators in the same formula may prove to be exceedingly difficult to interpret when assessing the result of the regression.

Additionally, the index proposed by Adserà & Pytliková is purely philological and should not be confused with the economic substance of the term linguistic distance. Linguistic distance in the economy is aimed to assess the relative cheapness or costliness of business communication and the cost of localization of commodities in international trade which is not always in direct relation to the proximity of two languages in the linguistic family tree (Chiswick, B., & Miller, P., 2005). For example, Polish and Ukrainian are linguistically close languages but use Latin and Cyrillic alphabet respectively; the same is true for Korean and Japanese with even more differences in writing systems that will undoubtedly increase the cost of localization. Two partners may be of different language families but have shared colonial past and enough citizens educated in the same colonial language which may prove to be vital for international trade communication. The same goes for significant or influential diasporas, the number of universities teaching specific language and other contributing factors that will provide the business environment with necessary specialists.

Given the above, to analyze the influence of linguistic distance on trade in the case of China the basic model used in this study will take the following form with only one dummy variable:

$$\ln T_{ij} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \ln(Y_{it}) + \alpha_2 \ln(Y_{jt}) + \alpha_3 \ln(D_{ij}) + \alpha_4 L_{ijt} + \varepsilon_{ijt} \quad (3)$$

Where T_{ij} – is the turnover of trade (sum of export and import) between country i and j (note that in this article i stands for China); t – is a year of data unitized in each example (from 2001 to 2018); Y_i, Y_j – is the Gross Domestic Product; D_{ij} – is the distance (in kilometers) between China and the specific trade partner; L_{ijt} – is the linguistic distance dummy variable; ε – is an error term.

Given the above, we propose to use L dummy variable as 0 for linguistic proximity (i.e. common language, a large

number of diaspora, etc.) and 1 for linguistic distance (i.e. no common language, no significant diaspora, etc.) since it can be misleading when existing distance yields a positive impact on total trade. To determine whether or not two countries are linguistically close or distant we propose to use 4 indicators: 1) the estimated size of diaspora; 2) similarity of the writing system; 3) level of institutional cooperation; 4) English language proficiency.

Table 1: Indicators composing the linguistic distance or proximity

Indicator	Proximity	Distance
Estimated size of the diaspora	Significant (more than 100 thousand people)	Mediocre or low (less than 100 thousand people)
Level of institutional cooperation	5 or more Confucius institutes or classes officially opened in the country.	Less than 5 Confucius institutes or classes officially opened in the country.
English language proficiency	Very High or High rank of EF EPI; English is an official national language	Moderate, Low, Very Low rank of EF EPI.
Similarity of the writing system	Usage of Chinese characters as an official writing system (similar) or extensive experience of its use in the past (mixed).	No official usage of Chinese characters either in the past or present (different).

The linguistic distance is unquestionably related to the size of the diaspora. In case of China this is further enhanced by the existence of so-called “Bamboo network” – a group of countries with particularly influential Chinese minority controlling business and influencing politics that forms an economic sphere of influence in Southeast Asia (Myanmar, Malaysia, Indonesia, Thailand, Vietnam, Philippines, Singapore) (Weidenbaum & Hughes, 1996). In this study, it is proposed to consider this indicator significant if the size of the Chinese diaspora is exceeding 100 thousand residents of the country in question.

A level of institutional cooperation is a flexible concept that should be approached individually for each country. The purpose of this indicator is to show whether or not the two countries are engaged in a deep and comprehensive partnership. This can be measured by examining the shared membership in international organizations, number of treaties, visits of delegations, consulates, shared history of colonial past, number of universities dedicated to studying language and culture, etc. In the case of China, it is reasonable to evaluate this indicator by comparing the number of Confucius Institutes in different countries. The Confucius Institutes were established to meet the sharp increase in global demand for Chinese language learning; their official mission is promoting cultural exchange and assisting in establishing business-ties with China (Hartig, 2016). By evaluating the number of Confucius Institutes in different countries it can be observed which partners are currently is of particular interest for the Chinese government and where businesses can expect additional language support in form of Chinese- or English-speaking translators trained or provided by Chinese government-funded organizations. By comparing the number of Confucius Institutes in different countries we propose that at

least 5 such establishments are sufficient to serve as an indicator of linguistic proximity.

A writing system is an important indicator that is often neglected in studies concerning the language factor of trade. Even if two languages are of the same origins different alphabet or input type may still be an obstacle that will increase the price of localization or even render the existing commodity impossible to be provided with language support for a particular market. Such an obstacle is fundamental for Asian countries that use Chinese characters and right-to-left horizontal type of input. Outside the Greater China (PRC, Hong Kong, Macao, Taiwan) the Chinese characters are officially recognized in Singapore and used as part of the writing system in Japan, while in Korea, Viet Nam, Malaysia, and Indonesia exist a strong historical tradition of their usage reinforced by the influential local diaspora that may also be considered as a factor of linguistic proximity (Gil, 2017).

Despite the differences between languages and cultures, English remains the universal de-facto language of business that may be used as an intermediary means of communication between business circles of two entirely different linguistic environments. But to achieve this both nations need to have significant English proficiency on the national scale. To determine whether or not the country in question may be considered to be English-proficient this study utilizes the EF English Proficiency Index (EF EPI) rankings as of 2019. If a country has High or Very High rank of EF EPI, it is considered to be of linguistic proximity, otherwise distance. It needs to be noted that China is of Moderate EF EPI rank and this indicator can only be considered supplementary and can't substitute other indicators.

According to the methodology described in Table 1 country need to meet at least two required indicators of

linguistic proximity to be considered “of no distance” to China, otherwise, the language dummy variable will remain 1.

Data sources

In this article 198 countries, administrative regions, territories, and dependencies were analyzed by using the described methodology in a timespan from 2001 to 2018 (data on diaspora was provided only for 2001 and 2011). Data for GDP was obtained from World Bank, commodities trade data was provided by International Trade Center,

information on the size Chinese diaspora was retrieved based on research conducted by Poston & Wong (2016) on the various statistical sources and estimations, the results of EF EPI is available at the official website of Education First, the number of Confucius Institutes can be found on the official Confucius Institute Headquarters website. Other necessary data was obtained by using CIA World Factbook. To analyze the results we utilize the method provided by Dr. Selim Raihan at the Capacity Building Workshop on Introduction to Gravity Modelling (Raihan, 2016).

Table 2: Countries and territories with linguistic proximity to China, 2018

Country / region	Estimated size of the Chinese diaspora	Confucius institutes / classes	English language proficiency	Similarity of writing system
	Thsd ppl	Number	Rank	Type of input
Australia	755	14 / 6	Native	Different
Belgium	9,01	6 / 0	Very High	Different
Brazil	252	10 / 3	Low	Different
Canada	1511	12 / 0	Native	Different
France	442	18 / 0	Moderate	Different
Germany	91	19 / 2	Very High	Different
India	129.74	4 / 2	Moderate	Different
Indonesia	8010	7 / 0	Low	Mixed
Italy	202	12 / 3	Moderate	Different
Japan	675	15 / 2	Low	Mixed
Malaysia	6541	4 / 1	High	Mixed
Netherlands	111.45	2 / 0	Very High	Different
New Zealand	149	3 / 0	Very High	Different
Philippines	1243	4 / 0	High	Different
Poland	6	6 / 1	Very High	Different
Rep. of Korea	24	23 / 5	Moderate	Mixed
Russian Federation	447	19 / 4	Low	Different
Singapore	2808	1 / 2	Very High	Mixed
South Africa	110	6 / 3	Very High	Different
Spain	141	8 / 0	Moderate	Different
Thailand	7513	16 / 11	Very Low	Different
United Kingdom	401	23 / 3	Native	Different
USA	4160	86 / 12	Native	Different
Vietnam	993	1 / 0	Low	Mixed
Hong Kong, China	Native	0 / 0	Moderate	Similar
Macao, China	Native	1 / 0	Moderate	Similar
Taipei, Chinese	Native	1 / 0	Moderate	Similar

Composed by author using the following sources: International Trade Center; EF Education First; Confucius Institute Headquarters (Hanban); Poston, D. L., & Wong, J. H. (2016); Gil (2017).

Analysis of results

It was revealed that there are currently 24 countries linguistically close to China along with the special economic regions (SAR) of Hong Kong, Macao, and Taiwan (see table 2 for detailed results). Among four indicators the most contributing to linguistic distance was the writing system similarity: 190 out of 198 analyzed countries do not use

Chinese characters on any level. 181 countries had less than 5 Confucius institutes, 170 countries do not have any significant Chinese diaspora, and 150 had lower Mediocre to Very Low English Proficiency.

According to the results of OLS regression (table 3), the coefficient on linguistic proximity is positive and highly significant in all four specifications.

Table 3: Result of the estimation of the proposed gravity model (3)

Variable	Description	OLS Coefficient	Std. Error	t	P
$\ln(Y_{it})$	GDP of China	0.6924056	0.0272449	91.23	0.000
$\ln(Y_{jt})$	GDP of j-partner in bilateral trade	0.9678351	0.0106087	25.41	0.000
$\ln(D_{it})$	Geographical distance	-0.554419	0.0396361	-13.99	0.000
L_{ij}	Linguistic distance	-0.445903	0.0754384	-5.91	0.000
-	Constant	-24.38958	0.8653709	-28.18	0.000
-	Number of observations	3505	-	-	-
-	R-squared	0.8214	-	-	-

Holding all other variables constant a 1% growth in GDP of China will result in 0.692% change in total trade with the respected partner country and 1% growth in GDP of a partner country will result in 0.967% change in total trade making the economy size of a partner country more significant to the amount of trade with China. Both geographical and linguistic have a negative impact on trade. In the case of geographical distance, a 1% positive change in distance will result in a loss of 0.554% of total trade with the respected partner. Linguistic distance is a binary indicator dummy variable and can only be 0 or 1. If the linguistic distance is 1 (meaning little to none language similarity with a said partner) this will result in loss of 56% $[(\exp(0.445903) - 1) \times 100 = 56]$ of total trade with China in comparison with a partner where linguistic distance yields 0 (Raihan, 2016).

Thus, other things being equal, we find that the volume of trade between the two countries is higher if their official languages are closer. These results hold for aggregate exports and imports. Linguistic distance yields a negative impact on trade and proves to be highly significant.

Conclusion

This article investigates the role of language factor (linguistic distance) on bilateral trade by using a set of four indicators aimed to depict linguistic distance or proximity of China and each of its 198 partners (countries, territories, and dependencies as provided in data of International Trade Center). The goal of this study was to propose a new approach at the measurement of linguistic distance or proximity which is currently described either as a simple dummy variable (or set of dummy variables) or as an independent quality index. By utilizing 4 indicators of linguistic distance (estimated size of the diaspora; a level of institutional cooperation; English language proficiency; similarity of the writing system) it was determined that there are currently 24 countries linguistically close to China.

To further address the research question, the enhanced gravity model was estimated by using the panel dataset constructed on trade flows, GDP and distance data from China and 198 source countries, from 2001 to 2018. According to the gravity model estimation results, bilateral trade flows between China and its partners are affected by the size of the economy (measured as the GDP), geographical and linguistic distance. The linguistic distance yields a significant negative impact on trade. This proves that the methodology offered in this study to measure linguistic distance is plausible and may be examined in consequent studies with other countries and languages. However, it

needs to be noted that the current method assumes that each of the proposed indicators has an equal impact on linguistic distance. Given the credibility of the method itself, it needs to be reexamined to further determine the weight or quality coefficient of each indicator in determining the dummy variable of linguistic distance.

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